

Abstract

This article takes the career of Spanish filmmaker Val del Omar (1904-1982) as a basis for analysing some of the crossroads between the psychologisation of modern culture and the development of cinematic art. Like Sergei Eisenstein or Jean Epstein, Val del Omar was an avant-garde director who resorted to psychological discourse to substantiate his aesthetic theories and proposals. As his creative life spanned the better part of the twentieth century, he was able to absorb many psychological premises into his theses, including theories around ethno-psychology, psychoanalysis, perception and empathy. As our analysis shows, those premises drove his aesthetic experimentation to limits beyond conventional cinema. More specifically, Val del Omar's heterodoxic theoretical and cinematic output focused on two features of psychology he deemed inherent to the new audiovisual media: perceptive automatism and the empathetic connection with the sublime. Building on those grounds, Val del Omar aimed to spur the development of freely willed individuals-viewers. Our conclusions stress the continuity between his psycho-aesthetic agenda and the social engineering characteristic of Western modernity, in conjunction with the construction, not wholly free of contradiction, of the model of subjectivity requisite to that endeavour.

Keywords: cinematographic theory, empathy, perception theories, psychoanalysis in film, ethno-psychology.

Psychologisation of Cinema: the Work of Val del Omar (1904-1982)

Starting in the last third of the nineteenth century with an agenda committed to urban settings and industrial development, modernity gave rise to new individual and collective experiences associated with mechanisation, mobility and acceleration (Connerton, 2009) in a number of socio-cultural (work, educational, clinical) domains. The advent of such experiences and their consequences for subjectivity caught the attention of both psychology and film, giving way to a new approach to psycho-aesthetics. Against the backdrop of the transformation of modern subjectivity, that dialogue between psychology and film can be thematically categorised in terms of two non-excluding historic-genealogical grounds compatible with certain dimensions of subjectivity. The first would address strategies for modelling and reproducing behaviour on screen, in turn involving the enlistment of representational and cognitive dimensions. That basis would connect into the origins of documentary or testimonial film, represented by the Lumière brothers and their interest in capturing the motion absent in painting and photography. Its theoretical development was undertaken by authors close to realism such as essayist Siegfried Kracauer (1889-1966) and critic André Bazin (1918-1958), for whom the value of film lay in its ability to authentically apprehend and mechanically reproduce events.

The second cornerstone would invoke the attentional, perceptive and affective dimensions. It would be aligned with the vision of cinema as amusement introduced by Georges Méliès (1861-1938), rooted in the illusionism of magicians' shows. It would likewise be akin to the theories posited by screenwriter Béla Balázs (1884-1949) or psychologists Hugo Münsterberg (1863-1916) and Rudolf Arnheim (1904-2007), who believed that the escape from reality afforded viewers was what determined the value of cinema (Arnheim, 1932/1933).

In light of that dual genealogical front, the encounter between psychology and film was clearly not involuntary. On the one hand, psycho-physiological research on perception had always

engaged in studying laws of optics, including the pre- cinematographic illusion of motion. And on the other, by the early twentieth century film was an inexcusable reference for interpreting the dynamics of a new subjectivity and creating formulas for psychological and social intervention suited to 'modern times'. Further to the findings of Max Wertheimer's (1880-1943) and Hugo Münsterberg's earliest experiments, even prior to the nineteen twenties psychologists were aware of the relevance of the visual arts to studies of perception and the potential of 'motion pictures', characterised by substantial power of persuasion (Pedro, 2013 & 211; Rieber & Kelly, 2013). That made the discipline ideal for application to domains such as advertising (military recruitment or consumption, for instance) and education (by heightening citizens' informed awareness).

Early psychology also left its imprint on European and American film studios and directors in the first decade of the twentieth century. Not only did it take centre stage in plots from the earliest feature films (*The Cabinet of Dr. Caligari*, *Dr Mabuse the Gambler*, *The Vampire of Düsseldorf*) (see Kracauer, 1947; Moreno, 2005), but proved to be a powerful tool for interpreting, justifying and orienting film creations. Filmmakers found in psychology a discourse that could afford cinema authority and theoretical legitimacy, in turn usable to convert what at the time was deemed artisanal entertainment into a sophisticated technique and art at the service of ideological, pedagogical and moral aims. By the mid- twentieth century, experimental studies were being authored, among others, by the *Filmologie* circle, in whose institutions cinema became a subject of academic analysis based on the oeuvre of psychologists such as Albert Michotte (1881-1965) and Serge Lebovici (1881-1965). From the times of pioneers such as David Griffith (1875-1948), Friedrich Murnau (1888-1931), Jean Epstein (1897- 1953), Serguéi Eisenstein (1898-1948) or Val del Omar himself, psychology roused much greater interest among filmmakers than cinema among psychologists.

The case at hand, Spanish director José Val del Omar, is paradigmatic of the colonisation of film by psychological discourse. A ese respecto, although we shall briefly contextualise Val del Omar's life and works (see Gubern, 2004; Sáenz de Buruaga and Val del Omar, 1992b), conviene

precisar que, desde el punto de vista metodológico, no nos interesa reivindicar o recuperar la figura de Val del Omar en los términos del “Gran hombre” propios de las historiografías reconstructivas y celebratorias. Muy al contrario, nuestra aproximación tiene un claro cariz teórico-genealógico (Rose, 1998) y parte de un Weberian analysis of his oeuvre (Hekman, 1983). Así, más allá de sus posibles logros singulares, tomamos a Val del Omar como un tipo “ideal type” weberiano que nos permite analizar dinámicas socio-históricas and pivotal issues determinantes del encounter between psychology and film.

One very interesting genealogical feature of Val del Omar’s production is its duration, given the director’s longevity, for it serves as a showcase of the relationship between psychology and film from their respective foundational stages through the nineteen eighties. Based on his works, our focus will be on mapping and analysing the terms of that extended relationship y los modelos de subjetividad que fueron ofreciendo. From that vantage point his papers were closely aligned with both his audiovisual oeuvre and the books in his personal library.³ Taking the analysis of all that material as a starting point, we drew a psycho-aesthetic map to divide Val del Omar’s oeuvre into five conceptual crossroads: unconscious, ethno-psychology, psycho-pedagogy, empathy (as perception and as mecha-mystics) and perceptive technologies. Our analysis found these questions to be interrelated and overlap throughout the author’s writings.

Brief biographical notes

Val del Omar was born in 1904 at Granada, a city in southern Spain characterized by historical-cultural tensions which would influence in the ethno-psychological sensitivity of his works: the Spanish religious tradition versus the European liberal modernity, the mechanistic theories versus the mystical feelings, etc. After a stay in Paris in 1921, he shot his first film, *Lucerito/En un rincón de Andalucía* [Lucerito/in a corner of Andalusia] (ca. 1925). The experience

served him to reflect on the mystical meaning of energy and its materialisation in cinema (Val del Omar, ca. 1940/2010, 1956, ca. 1970, 1980).

Beginning in 1930 Val del Omar developed an interest in the psycho-pedagogical features of cinematographic technique and enthusiasm for *kinaesthetic teaching*. He was drawn at just that time to the Institución Libre de Enseñanza (ILE), the Spanish liberal reform movement's primary psycho-pedagogical project. Through the ILE Val del Omar became involved in the pedagogical missions, an initiative in which groups of teachers and intellectuals visited Spain's most remote depressed areas.

The better part of his lectures and writings on pedagogy and film date from the first half of the nineteen thirties. The outbreak of the Spanish Civil War in 1936, however, drastically changed his life and career. Despite his involvement in the Republican liberal education project, Val del Omar eluded the post-war exile. As he was nonetheless required to recognise the new order (Val del Omar, ca. 1940/2010), he eventually reinvented himself as a professional in the Francoist regime's propagandistic and cinematographic machinery.

He settled in Madrid where he was granted a host of cinema technique-related patents and in the years that followed collaborated with many official institutions engaging in audiovisual media. He often verbalised his dissatisfaction about the difficulties and underestimation his work encountered due to the technical, institutional and economic constraints prevailing in contemporary Spain. That did not prevent Val del Omar from pursuing his creative bent, for he continued to produce short films such as *Aguaespejo granadino / La gran seguiriya (Ensayo audiovisual de plástica lírica)* (1951-1955) [Granada water mirror / the grand 'seguirya' (audiovisual essay on lyrical plastic art)], shown at the Berlin Film Fest where it met with praise from specialised film critics; *Fuego en Castilla (Tactilvisión del páramo del espanto)* (1957-1959) [fire in Castile (tactile vision of horror)]; and the unfinished *Acariño Galaico (De barro)* [Gaelic caress (of clay)].⁴

Together the three comprised an 'elementary triptych' or lyrical documentary on Spain (Val del Omar, ca. 1981) filmed using a highly innovative format, although with obvious connections to

the surrealism (Beard, 2010; Molina Barea, 2018). He addressed his theories on what he referred to as *meca-mística* [mecha-mysticism] and tactile vision. When in his sixties, Val del Omar would pioneer what has been deemed an extraordinary ‘post-cinematographic turnabout’ (Bonet, 2010/2015).

Affected by his wife’s death in 1977, Val del Omar lived thereafter in his laboratory, which had by then become both an ascetic workplace and a space for reflection (Tranche, 2012; Viver, 2010). He died in an automobile accident in 1984, before he was able to finish his short film *Acariño Galaico* [Gaelic caress] (Val del Omar & Codesal, 1961-1995) or the final chapter of his ‘elementary triptych’, *Ojalà* [I hope].

Val del Omar’s biography is characteristic of a creator caught in the tensions of his times, between technology and spirituality, artistic aspiration and material needs covered by patent production, conservatism and progressivism, globalisation and local concerns, alienating automation and the pursuit of new experience. His attempts to resolve those tensions, a constant presence in his life and work over three-quarters of a century, evolved with and fed on scientific-philosophical resources. In that regard, Val del Omar engaged in his own self-education based on extensive reading on the psychology of perception, pedagogy, psychoanalysis and bioanthropology, to name a few.

The Unconscious

The significance of the unconscious in Val del Omar’s work hinged on his conviction that instinct and affect-emotion prevailed over rationality in the pursuit of genuine knowledge. He consequently attributed more immediate and authentic communicative power to the pictures in motion that characterise film than to words (Val del Omar, 1932 - ca. 1970). Film as a language in its own right alternative to the verbal sort, a metaphor that had been around since Münsterberg’s times, was endorsed by Rudolf Arnheim (Pedro, 2013). In the nineteen twenties film was also

routinely regarded a type of unconscious or instinctive communication by authors such as Vachel Lindsay (1879-1931), Béla Balázs (1884-1949) and Serguéi Eisenstein (1898-1948). The disputed relationship between language and film has in fact been a constant throughout the history of the art (see Carroll, 1980/2012). The issue of inner discourse, explored in great depth by Lev Vygotsky's (1896-1934) social- historical school, was resorted to by theorist Boris Eijenbaum (1886-1959), for instance, to identify film images as unconscious rhetoric mediators (Eijenbaum, 1927/1982).

Val del Omar drew from another psychological school, perhaps the most common and inescapable for the artists of his day: Freudian psychoanalysis. Intellectuals appreciative of avant-garde art such as Antonin Artaud (1896-1948) and Walter Benjamin (1892-1940) had identified film as a vehicle that enabled unconscious content to emerge (Artaud, 1949/1972; Benjamin, 1931/2005; 1936/2008). Cinema was also viewed as a means to confront the individual with the extreme poly-sensory experience that Wagnerian opera had claimed for itself half a century earlier (Castro, Pizarroso and Morgade, 2005). It consequently seemed possible to elude the inevitability of verblatity, to speak in the same 'imaginative' terms as the unconscious in pursuit of individual freedom. In that vein, when Val del Omar came up with immersive and 'co-sensory' (visual, auditive, tactile, even olfactory and gustative) cinematographic techniques, he did so to expand viewers' conscience and awaken them from the passivity inherent in purely commercial messages.

Val del Omar was familiar with psychoanalysis, having read works ranging from Freud's earliest studies on the unconscious (which he mentioned, for instance, in Val del Omar, 1932-ca. 1970) to perspectives geared more to social concerns, such as defended by Herbert Marcuse (1898-1979) and Erich Fromm (1900-1980) (Ortiz- Echagüe, 2010b; Viver, 2010). At different times in the twentieth century, all those dimensions of psychoanalysis carried substantial weight in cinematographic critique and creation, ultimately crystallising in Christian Metz's (1977/1982) influential contributions. In the final third of his life, Val del Omar was most impressed by his study of sociological psychoanalysis (Sáenz de Buruaga, 2002/2015). That converged naturally on his fascination with the writings of new communication scholars such as Marshall McLuhan and Pierre

Teilhard de Chardin (1881- 1955), both of whom made heterodox use of psychoanalysis (Braga, 2016; Gustafson, 2015; Steinhart, 2008). Val del Omar may have invoked that reworked psychoanalysis to rethink the ways new worldwide culture and in particular audiovisual technologies were affecting the mentality and psychological aptitudes of contemporary communities.

Nonetheless, our author's position entailed crucial and constant departures from certain psychoanalytical (especially Freudian) assumptions. We believe that his notion of unconscious life was not Freudian, for he deemed it a beneficial, creative and eminently collective, rather than individual, current to be exploited. His objective was less individual freedom than union with all of humanity and even with absolute elements such as divinity and love (Molina Barea, 2018; Val del Omar, 1932-ca.1970, 1959a, 1959b, 1961, 1967/2010). Here, as in Chardin, the connection may have been closer to archetypal Jungian collective unconscious (on Jung's influence on film, see Bassil-Morozow, 2015). The impression, however, is that the use of psychoanalytical terminology enabled Val del Omar to align his theses on the unconscious and instinct more closely with contemporary rhetoric. His proposal could ultimately be deemed to rest on the nineteenth century notion of the 'collective soul'.

More specifically, Val del Omar's theses were reminiscent of an even older **notion**, *Völkerpsychologie*, present in the idealistic current inherited from romanticism and represented by authors such as Moritz Lazarus (1824-1903), Hermann Steinthal (1823-1899), Hippolyte Adolphe Taine (1828-1893) and Alfred Fouillée (1838-1912). That would implicitly obviate other more disputed versions of the collective personality or mentality of collectivist origin, such as defended by positivism's crowd psychology. Developed by Gustave Le Bon (1841-1931), Gabriel Tarde (1843-1904) and Scipio Sighele (1868-1913), among other authors, crowd psychology puts forward a notion of the collective unconscious clearly related to the Freudian **concept**, which Val del Omar appears to have ruled out.

Ethno-psychology

The dynamics of the collective unconscious of societies, peoples and crowds were of vital importance for late nineteenth and early twentieth century nationalist reformisms. But Spanish liberal reformism was fairly unusual. The theses of a minor post-Kantian thinker, idealist philosopher Karl Christian Friedrich Krause (1781-1832), introduced in the country by Julián Sanz del Río (1814-1869) (one of whose disciples, Giner de los Ríos, founded the Institución Libre de Enseñanza), were of particular significance in that regard (López Morillas, 1980). As premises compatible with those defended by the influential Anglo-Saxon positivist Herbert Spencer (1820-1903) were also in vogue, around the turn of the nineteenth century many Spanish intellectuals, especially those close to the Institución Libre de Enseñanza, identified with the label 'Krausopositivist' (Nuñez Ruiz, 1975; Blanco, 1997; Lissorgues, 2008 and 2009).

Krause's and Spencer's postulates were present especially in the notion of the 'social organism' on which three principles defended by Spanish liberalism hinged: a harmonious vision of Spanish society, a pantheistic and humanist conception of its future spiritual course and the guiding role of illustrated elites in that process. While stressing the poverty and lack of instruction that characterised commonfolk, political strategy also deemed that community to be the custodians of collective essence. The liberal vision was supplemented, then, with a romantic view on which a presumed Spanish psyche was built. The theoretical parentage exercised by Taine, Lazarus and Steinthal, referred to earlier, played a decisive role in the 'psychologisation' of social reality. That proved to be an essential process, for it justified the dependence of national regeneration on (educational, clinical, occupational) psychotechnical intervention (Castro, 2004).

Regenerationism was the umbrella movement covering Spanish reformist liberalism and its attempt to turn the page on the conclusive disappearance of the Spanish empire (territories such as Cuba and the Philippines gain their independence in 1898 with the intervention of the United States) and construct a modern and industrial nation-state. The work of reputed authors such as

writer Miguel de Unamuno (1846-1936), philosopher Ortega y Gasset (1883-1955), García Lorca and Ángel Ganivet can be included in that ethno-psychologically-oriented project for national reform. Val del Omar admired and knew them all, either personally or through their work (Val del Omar, n.d.-c, n.d.-b, 1956, ca. 1940/2010, 1932/2010, ca. 1960, ca. 1970/2010).

From their standpoint, the poverty and illiteracy of the lower classes was identified with the uncorrupted, unconscious and instinctive essence of the national soul. At a far remove from the positivist psychogenetic scaling that associated that primeval status with the insufficiencies of human nature (characteristic of primitive people or children and similar to those of animals), Val del Omar and Spanish Regenerationism interpreted it in cordial terms. That attitude was at odds with the model of subject and society typical of Western modernity, which for Val del Omar appeared to base everything on 'rationality', 'literacy' and the 'logic' of deliberation, the profit motive and, ultimately, progress and material development.

Val del Omar's psychological stance contended, in contrast, that the deepest strata of the mind, unmediated by discursive reasoning, were directly connected to the authenticity of experience and the genuinely human condition. While mechanisms favouring automatic and unthinking reaction, they happily also connected perfectly into the ability of film to assimilate and communicate reality *mechanically*. For Val del Omar, cinema was an instinctive language, a vehicle he associated with the automatism entailed in recording and perceiving motion pictures (Val del Omar, 1932-ca. 1970, 1934/2010, 1935, 1942, 1976). Como veremos, esta perspectiva influirá de forma determinante en su programa psicopedagógico.

The idea that as film is absorbed involuntarily it constitutes an ideal tool for spiritual education and civilising individuals and peoples who express the virginity of their irrationality was not new. It appeared, for instance, in *Manifesto della Cinematografia Futurista* [Manifesto of futurist cinematography] authored by Italian avant-garde poet Filippo Tommaso Marinetti (1876-1944). That writer identified the shortcomings of books as conveyors of thought and defended film as an alternative engine able to drive the education of the population at large and carry the national

project forward (Marinetti et al., 1916/2017). Val del Omar found in late nineteenth- early twentieth century Spanish commonfolk the prototype of a promising virgin illiteracy. In its ethno-psychological interpretations, Spanish Regenerationism portrayed that populace, albeit in somewhat ambiguous terms, as a people more prone to fantasy and imagination than to concept. The psychological roots for that propensity were generally assumed to lie in a natural reaction to harsh environmental conditions or to the Arabic substrate in their hereditary make-up.

Ganivet unhesitatingly supported the latter, ‘orientalising’ approach (Ganivet, 1897) and Val del Omar was keenly attuned to his fellow townsman’s proposal in what appeared to be a new episode of mistrust of modernity understood in the purely materialistic sense. From that position he emphasised the idea that Spain in general and Granada⁵ in particular were junctions where oriental instinct met with Western rationality (Val del Omar, 1935: 51).

Building on the undercurrents of institutionalist Krausism, Val del Omar’s project for national essence consisted in more than self-regulation of individual and even than the harmonious aims of the social project. At best, those two horizons were way stations on the route, via audiovisual technology, to absolute union in humanity, love and God. The pursuit of transcendence even entailed venturing into mysticism, which chimed well with the Spanish psyche (Val del Omar, 1935, 1959b). Acknowledging the absence of any major scientific-technical achievements, Spanish regenerationism highlighted the natural religiosity of that psyche as expressed in its grandest historic endeavours and artistic productions. As discussed below, Val del Omar would share that sensitivity to the point of labelling his system as ‘mecha-mystic’ (Val del Omar, 1956, 1959a, 1959b, 1961, 1962).

Pedagogy

Education was the social technology most often invoked by liberal reformist projects, Spanish institutionalist Krausism among them (Blanco, 1997). Psychology constituted its scientific

foundations. The goal was humanistic, comprehensive education, preferably focusing on art and aesthetics (Garrido & Pinto, 1996). The rationale, as explained by Jean-Marie Guyau (1854-1888) and Karl Groos (1861-1946), was that, where concepts and logic failed, art, given its evocation of empathy and feeling, constituted a direct, universal language, irrespective of level of schooling (Guyau, 1897; Groos, 1919). Aesthetic experience could, then, further harmony among social classes and even peoples around a shared ideal of humanity.

Consequently, education based on feeling, spontaneity and personality became a vivid, dynamic and personalised alternative to memory-based traditional instruction. In Val del Omar's own words:

“All children are born geniuses / caged in by public instruction / flattened by education / inhibited by unidirectional information / idiotised (sic!) by advertising / dehumanised and prostituted by technology. / But the sap is wise / and clear-sightedness a component of humble instinct / with a simple in vitro molecular connection / mysterious electronic clay can / enlighten a new world” (Val del Omar, n.d.-d: 1; see also Val del Omar, 1932-ca.1970: 4).

Val del Omar could have had any number of models (Pestalozzi, Fröebel, Dewey, Decroly, Montessori, etc.), although he deemed that the specific psycho- pedagogical potential of film had yet to be explored, even if experimental psychology was the discipline most requested to advance in that direction. He opted for a proposal known as *kinaesthetic pedagogy* (Val del Omar, 1932-ca. 1970) according to which film could be used as an anti-intellectual, instinctive communication medium that fostered a sort of harmonisation between the Freudian ‘It’ and ‘Id’. He believed that audiovisual techniques should move beyond mere sensory reactions to attain the true interiorised and sentimental goal.

In that respect Val del Omar concurred with other filmmakers such as Dziga Vertov (1896-1954) who deemed cinema an ideal medium able to inspire huge strides in human evolution, where

‘through the poetry of machinery we move from backward citizen to perfect electric man’ (Vertov, 1922/1985: 8). Nonetheless, Vertov himself was acutely aware of the issues roused by excessive commercialisation (Vertov, 1923/1985). According to another of Val del Omar’s contemporaries, film could instigate only lower psychological processes. Even where resolved in the sentimental realm, or for that very reason, it did not ensure high moral, civic or religious stature (Barbens 1914, Conde, 1933).

Val del Omar also believed that audiovisual media, with their vast influence, could induce psychological disorders and nervous morbidity (Val del Omar, 1962, 1967/2010) such as hypertrophy of the imagination or spiritual apathy, pathologies triggered by the contrast between splendid images and the misery of real life. His experience in **several** pedagogical missions, documented in his own films, and the observation of the effect of film on the ‘scantly cultivated’ minds of children and peasants, had revealed such risks (Val del Omar, 1934/2010, ca. 1960). Hence his reticent view of industrial and commercial cinema, rife in his opinion with scandalous normative or ‘horizontal’ messages, in which filmmakers participated in a conspiracy to domesticate and blunt the collective spirit. He set that against genuine cinema and ‘filmatists’, characterised by a morally higher calling and responsibility (Val del Omar, 1935, 1959a, ca. 1960, 1961, 1962, 1967/2010). The Spanish term he coined (‘*cinemista*’) might be interpreted as a hybrid of filmmaker (*cinéasta*), alchemist (*alquimista*) and mystic (*místico*) (Gubern, 2004).

In short, Val del Omar’s filmmaking was a pedagogical wager for genuine ‘entertainment’ and the ‘vertical’ vitalisation that the author also attributed to the Castilian spirit in its mystic pursuit of transcendence. Nonetheless, time gradually instilled in him a certain pessimism as he realised that the pedagogical scales were tilted toward the wrong side of history: non-reflective absorption of propagandistic messages and the loss of each individual’s singularity, translating into a spiritually numb population (Val del Omar, 1967/2010).

Empathy-Perception

As in most classic psychological treatises, the productions of the great theorists and creators of audiovisual works made sense from the logic of the philosophy of history, which constituted a necessary pathway for all of humanity to progress toward the ultimate goal, harmony. Normally, concerning psychological mechanisms, a subject was assumed to need to draw from certain resources and live through certain experiences to reach a stage of higher development. Empathy and perception were crucial to that process, as the connection between the individual organism and its referential whole depended on those two concepts. It was from that perspective that Val del Omar proposed film as the ‘supreme art of experience’ (Val del Omar, 1928, 1934), a contention he attempted to develop in terms of mecha-mystics, from a theoretical point of view, and several technical proposals, from an empirical point of view. The former might be understood as the theorisation of the con-fusion with the whole; the latter, as technical-perceptive resolutions of the ‘supreme experience’.

Empathy as mecha-mystics

Empathy (*emföhlung* in German) was a vital late nineteenth-early twentieth century psycho-aesthetic **notion**. Originating in German romanticism, it acquired major importance in the theorisation around modern subjectivity (Castro, Pizarroso & Morgade-Salgado, 2005; Jahoda, 2005; Debes, 2015; Ruiz, 2016). The idea was explicitly addressed by philosophers and psychologists such as Robert Vischer (1847-1933), Theodor Lipps (1851-1914), Jean-Marie Guyau (1854-1888), Hugo Münsterberg (1863-1916), Wilhelm Wundt (1832-1920) and Sigmund Freud (1856-1939). Empathy essentially assumed that human beings are able to sentimentally project their own state of mind onto entities, subjects and objects both, in their immediate surrounds. In aesthetic theory that meant that author and viewer had to upgrade a given work of art by projecting their own

emotional verticality onto it. Nonetheless, they could carry that further and merge their own subjectivity pantheistically with a higher entity: humanity, love, nature or God.

Val del Omar partook of that tradition. The handout for the screening of *Aguaespejo granadino /La gran seguriya* at the Berlinale (*Granadische Wasserspiegelungen: ein film von José Val del Omar*, 1956) explicitly associated the filmmaker's diaphonic technique, discussed later, with the German aesthetic informing the projection of feeling. The author underlined the following in his copy of Ricardo Cristobal's *La metamorfosis del ojo* [Metamorphosis of the eye] (1980) (Ortiz-Echagüe, 2010b):

“The term *Einfühlung* [...] was adopted by Robert Vischer in an attempt to explain aesthetic contemplation. Nothing we perceive acts on us on its own, but rather jointly, as an echo of the related elements we hold within” (Cristobal, 1980, cited in Ortiz-Echagüe, 2010b: 109).

Nonetheless, in contrast to more classical approaches, Val del Omar cast technical mediation in a primary role, accentuating its epiphanic purpose. As a result, his view of empathy materialised in a dual **concept**, mecha-mystics (Val del Omar, 1959b, 1961). The first component of that concept, mechanics, identified technological automatism with directly experiencing the whole, a sort of ‘mediatorless mediation’ that abstracted **ideas** and reasons to trigger an immediate, purely affective, connection with the surrounds. It was by no means intended to be a mechanistic and atomistic adaptation, as in Taylorism. It was, rather, a vivifying and mind-broadening experience that Val del Omar associated with film understood as time- and space-based art, a quality correlated to active perception and concomitantly to movement of the spirit (Val del Omar, n.d.-a, 1928, 1957). Those two movements, external or objective and related to cinematographic artefact (space, time, causality, screen formats, characters...) and internal or subjective (the viewer's own perception, attention, memory, imagination and emotion) consequently co-participated in a fluent play on mutual projective identification. That approach, historically deemed innovative in the cinematographic theories of authors such as Hugo Münsterberg (1916), Béla Balázs (1924/2010)

and Edgar Morin (1956/2005), continues to be present in the psychoanalytical theories about film prevailing today (Cohen, 2001; Coplan, 2006), which build on those mechanisms.

The second component of the notion, mysticism, aimed to draw viewers (the truth residing within) nearer to God-love unity (the beauty residing without) (Val del Omar, 1928 1959b, 1961). That rapprochement called for an intermediate stage entailing communion among peers, for which Val del Omar coined the term *aproximación* (play on words in Spanish between ‘*aproximación*’ [approach] and ‘*prójimo*’ [other human beings]) (Val del Omar, 1959a, ca. 1960, 1967/2010, 1976). Intersubjectivity was thus redefined as a way station on the path to transcendence. Val del Omar underscored the similarity between transcendent experience triggered by revelation and the religious ecstasy typical of Spanish spirituality (Losada, 2010). Significantly, Sergei Eisenstein also compared film to mystic experience in an essay on an El Greco painting (Eisenstein, 1942, 1949, 1987). In any event, above and beyond the reference to Spain, Val del Omar invoked the theses of his much admired Teilhard de Chardin, for whom the individual human psyche charts an upward course to union with the divine. In that process, technologies would be the prostheses able to amplify human biopsychosocial aptitudes. Chardin defined the alterations in perception and consciousness that arise as moments of metaphysical or mystical intuition (Teilhard de Chardin, 1955/1999; Steinhart, 2008).

The overlap between those premises and nineteen sixties and seventies counter-culture is no coincidence. Val del Omar may well have studied that movement while reading *The highest state of consciousness* (White, 1972). The cinematographic dimension of the New Age was an avant-garde movement known since the mid-nineteen sixties as ‘expanded cinema’, with which Val del Omar has been associated (Beard, 2010). Expansion referred not only to the extension of projection formulas and the development of film technique, but also to experience around altered feelings and amplification of consciousness (Beard, 2010; VanDerBeek, 1965). It naturally included the emerging drug culture as well, understood as a vehicle for experimentation and self-knowledge. The parallelism between psychotropic experience and some of Val del Omar’s proposals is obvious,

although his writings and films contain no reference to narcotics. In his essay 'Introducción a una nueva lengua' [Introduction to a new language] he called for television programmes to include recordings of youths revealing the reality of their subjective worlds and inter-connecting emotionally (Val del Omar, 1967/2010).

Perceptive techniques and technologies

Val del Omar defined film and communication media as psycho-physiological techniques (Val del Omar, 1962) and read widely about vision and the physics of light and colour. Nonetheless, his mecha-mystics required a theory of perception that, in our view, he not find in schools such as Gestalt (Arnheim, 1966, 1986), phenomenology (Merleau-Ponty, 1945/1964) or experimental aesthetics (Seashore, 1947), his most revered references. There were historic reasons for crossing the bounds of human perception in the wake of technological developments, after World War II, in fields such as micro- and telescopic optics and X-rays, not to mention the widespread psychotropic and extrasensory experience referred to above. In that context, Val del Omar described the need for super-vision (Val del Omar, n.d.-a, 1955-1959, 1963, 1967), a **concept** that might be variously interpreted to refer to a type of perception that extends beyond conventional sensory organs or simply the exploration of all the potential of audiovisual circumstance and its effects on subjects' life experience. Be that as it may, Val del Omar was a technical more than an theoretical researcher, consistently in pursuit of artefacts able to trigger the 'supreme experience' consisting in the projection of and union with the absolute.

In connection with that pursuit, his cinematographic oeuvre, while defended as art in motion, is neither narrative nor entertainment as routinely found in contemporary fictional films. In keeping with his disdain for conceptual and plotted motion pictures, Val de Omar did not tell stories in his short films (Val del Omar, 1951-1955, 1957- 1959) nor did he seek mere identification between viewers and characters which did, however, involve psychoanalytical postulates.

At times he even failed to present finished products, proposing in their stead *parables*, in the literal sense of the term, conceived as open audiovisual experiences (Val del Omar, 1967/2010). In short, the entire endeavour was at the service of perceptive alternation understood as sensory expansion.

With a view to expanding those sensations, Val del Omar authored a number of technical proposals with substantial psychophysiological implications. They materialised through his successive experiments with diaphony, tactile vision, apanoramic overflow and the cyclo-tactile energetic bionic optical device, analysed below.

From the outset, Val del Omar worked under the conviction that human beings are influenced by all the events in their surrounds. That led to his earliest experiments with the first perceptive technique: diaphony (Val del Omar, 1944). In contrast to the notion of the physical counterpoint afforded by stereophonics, based on two audio sources, his diaphonic system proposed a psychic counterpoint via two sources of ‘voices’ or a dialogue of sounds. One voice, positioned in front of viewers, would document the action on the screen, while the other, located at the rear, would act in opposition, reflecting the audience’s subjective emotion. The dialogue between the two would induce estrangement and heighten viewers’ consciousness, preventing them from assimilating the message irreflexively. Val del Omar testes that technique in *Aguaespejo granadino* /*La gran seguriya* and *Fuego en Castilla*.

From the nineteen fifties onward, Val del Omar’s experiments with the senses were supplemented by his second technical proposal: tactile vision. Again, it was tested in his acclaimed film *Fuego en Castilla*. He would go on to develop the technique over the years, associating it with his research on colour (Val del Omar, 1963, 1967). Uncomfortable with the idea of film as mere visual perception, Val del Omar aspired to make it an immersive synaesthetic spectacle. Practically from the very beginning, authors theorising about film such as Walter Ruttmann (1887-1941) with his urban symphony, Léopold Survage (1879-1968) with symphony in colour, Abel Gance (1889-1981) with his music of light and Germaine Dulac (1882-1942) with his visual symphony had been

aware of the synaesthetic potential of the new medium. Others such as Walter Benjamin (1936/2008) and Val del Omar's admired Marshall McLuhan (McLuhan, & Fiore, 1967) proposed the full identification of cinematographic visual experience with corporeality and the sense of touch.

Val del Omar adopted a radical approach in that respect. He posited that, with the use of suitable lighting techniques, he could generate a reflex arc able to convert visual into haptic sensations. His aim was to convey the actual experience of touch and possession of objects, a material encounter between the objective world exhibited and the subjective world activated (Val del Omar, 1955-1959, 1963). To use his own words:

“In the tactile-vision system we distinguish at least two types of lighting: one, impressionistic and searching, inherently tactile, and the other expressionistic, characteristic of tactile sensation generated by our contact with surrounding object matter. This latter type of lighting carries objective information on that real and palpable world” (Val del Omar, 1963: 4).

The third technique deployed by Val del Omar to broaden his multisensory exploration in the nineteen sixties was what he called ‘apanoramic’ overflow of the image (Val del Omar, 1957). He addressed it as a new technique for psychological relief imaging based on projections governed by the same mechanisms as human sight: one, a central or ‘foveal’, focused and documentary image, and the other a concentric ‘extra-foveal’ image that flowed off the screen upward toward the ceiling, outward toward the walls and downward toward the audience. That latter projection would consist in abstract images, representing subjective emotion. As in diaphony and tactile vision, apanoramic overflow sought viewers’ active participation in the spectacle, consistently aiming to bring the objective and subjective worlds into close visionary understanding. He also put that technique in practice when he screened *Fuego en Castilla* [fire in Castile] at the 1961 Cannes International Film Festival (Tranche, 2020).

With the development of audiovisual technology from the nineteen seventies onward, Val del Omar found further reason to believe in the unlimited expansion of multisensory experience. Finally, his speculation revolved around his totalising *picto-luminic-audio-tactile* approach, the apparent culmination of synaesthetic potential (Herreruela Ruiz, 2014). That approach would also embrace a new interest in cybernetics and in particular the bionics of authors such as Lucien Gérardin (1968), who sought to artificially replicate natural systems. Based on those grounds, Val del Omar designed a Cyclo Tactile Energetic Bionic Optic Device, the conceptual basis for which was clearly set out by Rafael Tranche (Val del Omar, 1976).

The design of the respective bionic optical device included an anamorphic lens attached to a support rotated on its axis by a motor, along with a projector positioned in opposition to the rest of the assemblage. Anamorphic deformation and constant motion created volumetric, embossed, constantly changing images.

Integrating his prior concerns on empathy and perception into these new ideas, Val del Omar introduced the term ‘bioelectronic mysticism’ (Val del Omar, 1971) in which the ego was diluted in new communication techniques.

Conclusion

Como sugeríamos en la introducción, la figura histórica Val del Omar no es tan valiosa por sí sola para la historia de la psicología o el cine como ilustrativa de la mutua influencia y, con ella, la relevante y caleidoscópica encrucijada para la subjetividad moderna constituida entre ambos dominios. Val del Omar’s psycho-aesthetic theory runs parallel to the transformation of psychological discourse between the late nineteenth century and the nineteen sixties, from ethno-psychology or psycho-physiology to psychoanalysis or the psychology of perception. That final notion was actually never free of the tensions in which Val del Omar himself took such interest. As Psychology of perception itself, he pondered over whether perceptive experience is mediated or

immediate, mechanical or proactive, constructed or realistic, deductive or inductive, elemental or holistic. At the same time, the psychology of art followed a more linear historic course from mid-nineteenth-century metaphysical aesthetics to the experimental aesthetics in place in the nineteen twenties (Mitry, 1997). Such historic processes cannot in any event be understood without reference to the major scientific-philosophical, politico-ideological and historic-cultural structures in which psychological pursuits are inevitably enveloped. Despite experimental aesthetics, however, and with the exceptions of humanistic psychology and psychoanalysis, the relevance of affective-emotive issues and their association with the art world gradually waned in mainstream psychology after the nineteen thirties, compared at least to their status in the pioneering stages of the discipline (Castro, Pizarroso y Morgade-Salgado, 2005).

Nowadays, more general attention is being dispensed to affective experience prompted by the advent of postulates such as emotional intelligence, positive psychology and coaching. Art and cinema appear to be rousing renewed interest, although perhaps attendant upon a more general concern for new audiovisual technologies (see Mitry, 1997; Persson, 2003; Pulaki, 2018; Rieber, 2012; Shimamura, 2013; Tan, 2018).b

Be that as it may, as Val del Omar's oeuvre shows, film has never ceased to resort to psy discourse and practice, to the extent that cinematic theory has even been a historic refuge for the psycho-aesthetic exploration of a wide spectrum of perceptive and emotional dimensions. Thanks to film, since the late nineteenth century modern subjective experience has consistently been the object of aesthetic knowledge (de Carvalho, Passini & Baduy, 2015), in much the same way as thanks to psychology that experience has been a constant object of scientific knowledge.

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3 Val del Omar's writings tend to be obscure or heterodox. Most is found in lectures and scattered manuscripts, some posthumous. It has nonetheless fortunately been conserved in archives, many of which are accessible on a website managed by Eugeni Bonet (undated), www.valdelomar.com, a catalogue uploaded by the Queen Sofia National Museum, <http://catalogo.museoreinasofia.es/>, the filmographic collection on <https://multidoc30.wordpress.com/fondo-filmografico-val-del-omar/>, and the listings compiled by Ortiz- Echagüe (2010b), Saénz de Buruaga & Val del Omar (1992a; 1992b) and Duque (2015). That Val del Omar's cinematographic production has been analysed by a number of authors (Herreruela Ruiz, 2014; Losada, 2010; Romero, 2014; Sorolla-Romero & Loriguillo-López, 2016; Vázquez-

Medel, 1995), but his written works have received scant attention. Otherwise, the inventory of Val del Omar's library was published by Javier Ortiz-Echagüe (2010b) and in the PhD. thesis authored by Javier Viver (2010). Ortiz- Echagüe (2010a) noted that his catalogue lists the works found in Val del Omar's last workplace (his 'picto-luminic-audio-tactile' laboratory) and the ones conserved in the María José Val del Omar and Gonzalo Sáenz de Buruaga Archive.

10 4 Val del Omar, J. (1951-1955). *Aguaespejo granadino / La gran seguiriya* [Water-mirror of Granada / The great 'seguirya'] [Short-Film]. Vimeo. <https://vimeo.com/462224807>. Val del Omar, J. (1957-1959). *Fuego en Castilla (Tactilvisión del páramo del espanto)* [Fire in Castile (Tactile Vision of the wasteland of fear)] [Short-Film]. Youtube.https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EwOd2TFuAlw&ab_channel=emerson%EC%9D%B4%EC%A2%85%EC%98%A5. Val del Omar, J., & Codesal, J. (1961-1995). *Acariño Galaico (De barro)* [Galician caress (Of clay)] [Short-Film]. Youtube.https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=26nc_DgepXA&ab_channel=An%C3%A1lisisyCr%C3%ADticaUNLP

11 5 Granada was the Islamic emirate in Iberia until its conquest by King Ferdinand and Queen Isabella in 1492 drove unification of the Christian kingdoms co-existing on the peninsula.